

USING INTERACTIVE LEARNING METHODS IS A REQUIREMENT OF TIME

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Abstract. *The article says about the need to work with today's youth studying in secondary schools and universities in our country, using not only traditional, but also modern, innovative technologies. One of these technologies is interactive teaching methods.*

Key words: *worldview, the future of the Renaissance, web designers, testers, system administrators, KIBERone, BigData specialist, IT specialists and robotics.*

Аннотация. *В статье говорится, о необходимости работы с нынешней молодёжью, обучающихся в общеобразовательных школах и вузах нашей страны, с использованием не только традиционных, но и современных, инновационных технологий. Одной из таких технологий являются интерактивные методы обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *мировоззрение, будущее Ренессанса, веб-дизайнеры, тестировщики, системные администраторы, KIBERone, специалист по работе с BigData, IT-специалисты и робототехники.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada mamlakatimizdagi umumta'lim maktablari va oliy o'quv yurtlarida tahsil olayotgan bugungi yoshlar bilan nafaqat an'anaviy, balki zamonaviy, innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda ishlash zarurligi haqida so'z boradi. Ana shunday texnologiyalardan biri o'qitishning interfaol usullaridir.*

Kalit so'zlari: *Outlook, Uyg'onish davri kelajagi, veb-dizaynerlar, testerlar, tizim ma'murlari, KIBERone, Big Data mutaxassisi, IT mutaxassislari va robototexniklar.*

“School teachers, professors and teachers, scientific and creative intelligentsia, we consider the four most important pillars in the formation of the era of the new Renaissance”.

(Sh.M. Mirziyoyev)

Introduction.

The President of our country, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, in one of his interviews, emphasized that “Today, a new time is coming in the field of education and upbringing, in the life of our children. In our time, every teacher, educator, teacher of the university must have deep knowledge and a broad outlook, actively master the latest achievements of science, education and introduce them into the educational process, in a word, must be the foremost representative of our time and society.

The systems of preschool, school, higher and secondary specialized education, scientific and cultural institutions are four interconnected links of the future Renaissance. We consider kindergarten teachers, school teachers, professors and lecturers, scientific and creative intelligentsia to be the four most important pillars in the formation of the era of the new Renaissance.” [1.1]

Literature analysis and methodology.

According to statistics, in Uzbekistan, young people under 30 years old make up 60% of the population. In a few years, they will become the largest labor force in Uzbekistan, providing a unique opportunity to bring the country to a new level of socio-economic development.

Today, the attention and desire of the youth of our country to acquire knowledge has increased significantly.

At present, every young person understands that his future depends on himself, on his level of knowledge. Therefore, not only in big cities, but even in provincial towns and villages, our youth strives to additionally engage in self-education with the help of the Internet, to consolidate their knowledge in various educational centers.

Discussion.

Most of our young people are fluent in English and other foreign languages, are well versed in technology, and have excellent computer skills.

New professions are emerging as mobile app developers; cloud architects; system analysts; specialists in the field of artificial intelligence; web designers; testers; system administrators; Big Data specialist, IT-specialists and robotics.

Parents from the age of 6 send their children to different programming schools for children KIBER one, robotics, various educational centers where they teach languages, programming and etc.

And in order to educate worthy successors who lead their own and our future, in order to reach and stand along with such developed countries as the USA, China, Japan, Germany and the UK, each teacher must set and implement the following tasks:

- improve your teaching skills;
- pay more attention in the classroom to the presentation of new knowledge;
- determine students' knowledge of a new subject, provide preliminary

information specific to the subject:

- effectively use technical teaching aids, electronic textbooks and other materials;

- choose the right methods of work:

- be able to use the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice:

-accelerate the development of research, the implementation of their results in the educational process:

-conduct trainings on the formation of these activities and their use in practice:

- use the latest achievements of science and technology:

Currently, modern, innovative technologies are widely used in the learning process.

One such technology is interactive teaching methods.

The word "interactive" comes from the Latin "inter" - between, "to act", connection, closeness. The purpose of using interactive methods is to make the lessons interesting, meaningful, and most importantly, effective. When using interactive methods, students increase their level of knowledge, interest in science, develop their personality, and increase responsibility for the learning process.

Also, it should be noted that interactive methods in universities are designed to deepen, expand, clarify, consolidate and develop lecture knowledge during practical exercises.

It is known that for a good mastery of knowledge, the old method is not enough: just reading, listening and writing down, you need to actively work on this material, think it over, conduct a discussion, and perform auxiliary tasks.

Currently, one of the main tasks for us, teachers, is to develop the student's ability to work independently. When using interactive methods, all mental processes of perception, consciousness, attention, memory, intuition, mind, imagination, and thinking of students are involved. All of the above mental faculties are activated and are directed to the search, perseverance and development of their thoughts to solve the

problem. In this case, the intensity, the tendency of the material to understand increases, and the result becomes more effective.

The article presents some of the latest pedagogical technologies that can be used by teachers of secondary schools and university teachers in their pedagogical activities. So, when fixing the topic “Members of a sentence” or “Parts of speech”, the teacher can conduct an assignment using the table:

Method number 1. "Learning to distinguish".

Do students need to write the parts of speech in the first column, and the members of the sentence in the second? A hint is given at the bottom of the table: the names of parts of speech and sentence members. Thanks to this method, students remember well what parts of speech and members of a sentence are, which makes it possible for them not to confuse them.

№	Parts of speech	Members of the proposal
1.	Noun	Subject
2.	Adjective	Predicate
3.		
4.		
5.		
6.		

(Particle, addition, noun, preposition, interjections, subject, adjective, participle, definition, verb, modal words, state category words, conjunction, circumstance, numeral, onomatopoeic words, gerund, predicate, pronoun, adverb).

Method number 2. "Fill in the table".

This task can be given for independent work of students, after studying the topic: “Independent and service parts of speech”, as a result of which the teacher can find out the level of mastering the new topic by students. And it should be noted that this task will take a little time.

Independent parts of speech	What do they mean?	What questions do they answer?	Examples
Noun			
Adjective			
Verb			
Numerals			
Pronoun			
Adverb			

Service parts of speech	Examples
Prepositions	
Particle	
Interjection	

Method number 3. "Listen and complete"!

To develop the attention and memory of pupils and students, in the classroom of Russian or foreign literature, you can use the "Listen and complete!" method.

When using this method, students carefully listen to an audio recording of a poem or some short text, then fill out a printed version of the poem they listened to, where students must fill in the missing words. With this method, students, already when they get acquainted with one or another poetic work, memorize it by 30 percent, which makes it easier for him to memorize it.

For example:

A.S. Pushkin.

In the depths of Siberian ores...

In the depths of the Siberian ...

Keep proud patience

Your mournful work will not be lost

And the doom is high....

Unfortunately faithful sister,

Hope in the dark...,

Wake up cheerfulness and fun,

Will come ... it's time:

Love and friendship up to you

They will reach through the gloomy ...,

As in your ... holes,

My free voice is coming.

... the heaviest will fall,

The dungeons will collapse - and freedom

You will be gladly received at the entrance,

And brothers ... they will give you back.

Note: Here you need to skip such words that are rarely or not used at all in modern speech, followed by a search for the meaning of the lexical meaning of these words in explanatory dictionaries. When using this technique, students get acquainted with explanatory dictionaries and learn to work with them.

Method number 4. "When the numbers speak"

This method is useful when working in groups. This type, like the previous methods given, trains the attention and memory of students.

For independent reading in groups, students are given the text of a biography of a writer or poet, which includes the main facts from his life and work, such as birth, origin, education, service, work, family relationships.

After reading the text (biography of the poet or writer being studied), the participants must, in the paper prepared by the teacher, with the dates entered in it, remember and write down from the previously read text what happened in the life of this writer on the date indicated in the table.

Pushkin Alexander Sergeevich (1799 - 1837)

Key dates of life and creativity

1799, May 26 (June 6) - was born in Moscow in the family of a retired major Sergei Lvovich Pushkin and his wife Nadezhda Osipovna (nee Hannibal).

1811-1817 - studying at the Tsarskoye Selo Lyceum.

1814 - first publication. The poem "To a friend of a poet" in the journal "Bulletin of Europe", No. 13.

1817–1820 – Petersburg period. Graduation at the Tsarskoye Selo Lyceum, service in the Collegium of Foreign Affairs.

1824-1826 - exile in Mikhailovskoye.

1825 - the poem K *** was written ("I remember a wonderful moment ...")

November 7 - the tragedy "Boris Godunov" is over

1831 - wedding with Natalya Nikolaevna Goncharova.

1837, January 27 - a duel with Dantes on the Black River. He died in St. Petersburg and was buried in the Svyatogorsk Monastery in the Pskov province.

1837, January 27,	1831	1824	1811–1817	1814

1799, May 26 (June 6)	1825	1824–1826	1817–1820

Method number 5. "Round table".

This method is often used, for example, when repeating a topic covered, groups are given sheets with the inscription "Parts of speech". Students must write on a piece of paper one part of speech, what question they answer, what they can be in a sentence and make a sentence with this part of speech. At the end, the answers are checked, incorrect answers are crossed out and points are given to the whole team.

Method number 6. "Black box".

Students choose cards with tasks of varying complexity and answer questions on their own.

For example, when passing in non-linguistic universities the topic "Expression of subject-predicate relations. Expression of qualification characteristics of a person (object, phenomenon). On separate sheets with the task: "Compose and write down sentences with these words as subjects." Each of the team members must read the sentence he composed and prove that the given word plays the role of the subject in the sentence.

1. We are with a friend.
2. One of the students.
3. Lots of books.
4. The majority of participants in the meeting.
5. Many of the teachers.
6. Twenty people.
7. Our group.
8. Ten years.
9. Car.
10. Something incomprehensible.
11. Reading.
12. Five.
13. Three friends.
14. Igor Andreev.
15. Smoking.
16. Three minutes.

Method number 7. I know. I want to know. I Learned

Among the wide variety of methodological techniques, educational technologies, teaching strategies, I know. I want to know. I learned. method occupies a special place,

which is aimed at developing independent critical thinking of students. What is I know. I want to know. I Learned.?

I know. I want to know. I learned is an interactive technique aimed at developing feedback in the cognitive process, which is deciphered as follows: I know. I want to know. I learned. The relevance of using this method is “to intensify student learning using new pedagogical and information technologies that contribute to the development of creative abilities, the education of an intellectual and independently thinking person who is able to navigate, set and solve problems.”

The I know. I want to know. I learned method is very interesting, effective, increases the interest of students and activates them in the study of the Russian language, as well as the development of speech and the formation of the ability to clearly and concisely express their thoughts both orally and in writing at the same time, and also helps to control the work of each student in the classroom, his understanding and interest in the topic being studied.

When using the I know. I want to know. I learned table in the educational process, there is a two-way activity: both on the part of the teacher and on the part of the students.

In the course of filling out the table, students learn to correlate the already familiar and the new, to determine their cognitive needs, while relying on the information they already know.

Filling in the table I know. I want to know. I learned.

Students draw a table in their notebooks and on the board, which they will fill out during the entire lesson.

I know	I want to know	I learned

The 1st stage of the lesson. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher sets the task for the students: to remember what they know about the issue being studied (the topic being studied), i.e. at this stage, there is a call in the memory of students already known I know I learned I want to know, a call of interest in a new topic, based on the answers of students on the material covered, the column “I know” is filled in.

Students make a list of what they know or think they know about the topic. Through this primary activity, the student determines the level of his own knowledge, to which a new stage is gradually added.

The 2nd stage is the comprehension stage. At this stage, new information is being processed. After filling in the “I know” column, new questions are formulated, the

answers to which students would like to receive after studying the topic. They are written in the second column. This is where the teacher's help is important, he should motivate students to reason and arouse interest in new information:

“What else would you like to know”?

“What can you learn in class today”?

This method can be applied when studying the topic in national groups of language universities. To do this, a table is drawn in notebooks and on the board, which will be filled in during the entire lesson.

Here is a phonetic transcription of the text.

Graphic entry. phonetic notation.

I learned to live simply, wisely, [ai le:nd tu liv simply,vaysli]

Look at the sky and pray to God, [luk et the skay end prey tu gad]

And long before the evening to wonder, [end long bifo: zi evening to uonde]

To relieve unnecessary anxiety. [tu rili:v annesesry engzaity]

At the beginning of the lesson, based on the answers of students on the material covered, the “I know” column is filled in.

Immediately, after filling in the “Know” column, new questions are formulated, the answers to which students would like to receive after studying the topic. They are written in the second column.

Finally, the teacher explains, on the basis of specific examples, transcription in the university curriculum. Then the students conduct an independent transcription of the words given by the teacher in notebooks and on the blackboard.

Conclusion

At present, each student should be able to independently acquire new knowledge, apply it in practice to solve the tasks; work with various information, analyze, generalize; be able to critically look for rational ways to solve problems. Methods aimed at activating the thinking of students, characterized by a high degree of interactivity, motivation and perception of the educational process, and help:

- activate the cognitive activity of students:
- to develop the creative activity of students:
- improve the effectiveness of the educational process.

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